

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Carbohydrate Polymer Technologies and Applications

journal homepage: www.sciencedirect.com/journal/carbohydrate-polymer-technologies-and-applications

Injectable hyaluronic acid/nanohydroxyapatite composite hydrogels for localized drug delivery and bone repair

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Injectable hydrogels
Hyaluronic acid
Hydroxyapatite nanoparticles
Strontium ranelate
Local drug delivery
Osteoporotic bone repair

ABSTRACT

Bone repair, especially in osteoporotic bone fractures, remains a clinical challenge due to poor bone tissue quality and limited self-regeneration capability. Injectable hydrogels with drug delivery functionality offer an advanced strategy by enabling localized, sustained therapy with improved bioavailability and reduced systemic side effects. In this study, for the first time, injectable, biodegradable composite hydrogels composed of covalently crosslinked hyaluronic acid (HA) and nanohydroxyapatite (nHAp), either unmodified or loaded with strontium ranelate (SrRan), were developed for bone repair applications.

These hydrogels could provide dual functionality by enabling localized, sustained drug delivery and supporting bone repair. The effect of nHAp content (0–70 wt%) on swelling, gel fraction, morphology, enzymatic degradation, mechanical and rheological properties, and injectability of the developed hydrogels was comprehensively evaluated. SrRan release kinetics were evaluated in three composite hydrogel formulations (30%, 50%, 70% SrRan-nHAp) to assess the influence of nanoparticle content on release rate and sustained delivery performance. All hydrogels exhibited shear-thinning behaviour, low injection forces (< 2.5 N) for manual delivery, and rapid post-injection viscosity recovery. Enzymatic degradation (with hyaluronidase) confirmed gradual hydrogel degradation with release of HA oligomers. SrRan-loaded composite hydrogels provided sustained SrRan release over 56 days. *In vitro* assays with NIH3T3 fibroblasts and MC3T3 preosteoblasts demonstrated excellent cytocompatibility of SrRan free HA/nHAp composite hydrogels across 0–70 wt% nHAp. Overall, the fabricated composite hydrogels demonstrated a versatile platform for bone repair, offering drug delivery functionality.

1. Introduction

Bone remodelling dysregulation leads to osteoporosis, projected to affect 263 million by 2034 (Kim et al., 2020; Ressler et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2023). This metabolic bone disease often leads to complications such as fractures and critical-sized bone defects (Hejazi et al., 2021; Nauth et al., 2018). Current clinical strategies, including autografts and commercially available bone graft substitutes, offer limited regenerative capacity and therapeutic effect, especially in osteoporotic bone, where poor tissue quality impairs healing, further highlighting the need for advanced bone biomaterials (Kim et al., 2020; Sohn & Oh, 2019). This has motivated the development of injectable, bioactive bone biomaterials with targeted drug delivery capabilities, designed for

minimally invasive application to fill irregular bone defects and promote therapeutic bone regeneration.

Strontium ranelate (SrRan) has a dual mode of action: it promotes bone formation by stimulating osteoblast replication, differentiation, and survival, while simultaneously reducing bone resorption by inhibiting osteoclast activity and inducing osteoclast apoptosis (Querido et al., 2016). However, SrRan has poor oral bioavailability (~25%) and systemic side effects at high doses (2 g/day), including headaches, nausea, diarrhoea, gastrointestinal discomfort, and skin allergies, which limit its long-term clinical use (Chiang et al., 2021; Marx et al., 2020; D. Zhang et al., 2019).

Localized SrRan delivery via biodegradable carriers, such as micro/nanoparticles (Loca et al., 2016; Higino & França, 2022; Loca et al.,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carpta.2025.101030>

Available online 20 October 2025

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2018), polymeric/ceramic scaffolds (Bai et al., 2023; Diaz-Rodriguez et al., 2018; Gong et al., 2022), and composite systems (Galotta et al., 2024; Lu, 2024; Svarca et al., 2022), target bone defects while addressing poor vascularization (Lv et al., 2022) and limited drug bio-distribution (Paladini & Pollini, 2022), thereby minimizing systemic toxicity (Sheng et al., 2023; Svarca et al., 2022). However, few studies have reported SrRan-loaded injectable systems.

Over the past decade, extensive research has focused on developing biodegradable, injectable delivery systems, particularly hydrogels based on natural biopolymers, such as hyaluronic acid (HA), gelatine, chitosan, and alginate, as promising carriers for therapeutic agents (Salehi et al., 2023). These systems combine biocompatibility, extracellular matrix (ECM) mimicking architecture, tunable mechanical properties, and minimally invasive delivery, enabling localized sustained drug release in complex bone defect geometries (Liu et al., 2017). Among these, HA-based injectable hydrogels have emerged as versatile biomaterials for bone tissue engineering due to their intrinsic biocompatibility, biodegradability, anti-inflammatory activity, and interaction with bone cells and growth factors (Petit et al., 2025a; Torresan et al., 2025; Zhai et al., 2020). HA is a naturally occurring, linear, non-sulfated glycosaminoglycan (GAG), naturally present in the ECM, composed of a repeating disaccharide unit of d-glucuronic acid and β -1,3-linked N-acetyl-d-glucosamine. HA numerous of advantages over other polysaccharides. It is FDA-approved as an injectable filler and widely used in biomedical applications (Bayer, 2020; Donneys et al., 2019; Hwang & Lee, 2023; Petit et al., 2025). HA actively regulates angiogenesis, wound healing, and inflammation (Chen et al., 2024; Senobari et al., 2024), processes that are essential for bone regeneration. It is also bioresorbable through enzymatic degradation by hyaluronidases (Patil et al., 2023), and can be easily functionalized via its carboxyl and hydroxyl groups to incorporate bioactive molecules (Senobari et al., 2024). However, HA alone lacks the intrinsic osteogenic capacity and insufficiently supports bone regeneration. To address this limitation, inorganic bioactive fillers such as calcium phosphates and bioactive glasses have been incorporated to improve mechanical integrity and cell-hydrogel interactions (Andronescu et al., 2016; Ielo et al., 2022; Kikani et al., 2023; Valdez et al., 2022; Zhai et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2022). Nano-hydroxyapatite (nHAp) is a bioactive and biocompatible nanomaterial that closely mimics the mineral component of natural bone, displaying unique chemical and structural similarities to bone apatite. In bone regeneration applications, nHAp is valued for its osteoconductive properties, capacity to promote osteoblast adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation, and ability to induce mineralization and bone tissue formation (Zaffarin et al., 2021; Mo et al., 2023; Shi et al., 2021). nHAp can also serve as a controlled drug delivery system due to its negative surface charge, which can attract drug molecules (Du et al., 2021). Therefore, in this study, injectable HA/nHAp composite hydrogels have been proposed as a promising biomaterial with drug delivery functionality for therapeutic bone regeneration. To date, only limited studies have explored injectable HA/nHAp-based hydrogel systems for targeted drug delivery and bone repair. Reported examples include injectable oxidized HA/HAp hybrid particles containing carboxymethyl chitosan hydrogels (Tan et al., 2022), nHAp and bone morphogenetic protein (BMP-2) containing thiol-modified HA (Hachinohe et al., 2022), modified gelatin and HA-based hydrogels encapsulating nHAp and human adipose-derived MSCs (Lee et al., 2024), and injectable thiolated HA hydrogels delivering lithium-doped nHAp (Y. Luo et al., 2024). However, only a few studies have explored the potential to incorporate SrRan or other drugs into the hydrogel and composite hydrogel systems to achieve dual functionality - bone tissue regeneration combined with local, sustained therapeutic drug delivery. Such examples include nanoencapsulated SrRan containing chitosan/alginate/fibrin hydrogels (Deepthi et al., 2016), SrRan-loaded sodium alginate/collagen hydrogels (Su et al., 2024). For example, Svarca et al. (Svarca et al., 2022) developed SrRan-loaded calcium phosphate nanoparticles incorporated into HA hydrogels crosslinked with 1,4-butanediol diglycidyl ether

(BDDE). However, systematic evaluation of HA hydrogels incorporating SrRan-loaded nHAp and crosslinked with 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride and N-hydroxysuccinimide (EDC/NHS) by targeting -COOH groups has not been studied.

These limited studies could be particularly associated with the challenges of designing homogeneous hydrogel/nanoparticle systems. Inadequate dispersion of nanoparticles into the hydrogel network during gelation can result in uncontrolled drug release profiles, necessitating careful selection of the appropriate preparation strategy (Ahmad et al., 2024; Yoon et al., 2025). Additionally, insufficient crosslinking may lead to nanoparticle leaching and compromise the mechanical integrity of the hydrogel. EDC/NHS crosslinking chemistry was selected for HA-based hydrogel fabrication in this study due to its advantages, including mild aqueous reaction conditions, low cytotoxicity from water-soluble by-products, robust and tunable mechanical properties, and controllable enzymatic degradation, all essential for sustained drug release and tissue integration in bone repair (Khunmanee et al., 2017; Z. Luo et al., 2023; Schanté et al., 2011; Yang et al., 2016). Hydrogels were formed *in situ* by applying EDC/NHS chemistry to a pre-synthesized nHAp or SrRan-loaded nHAp suspension. This approach enabled uniform nanoparticle distribution, high loading capacity (up to 70 % of nHAp in the HA network), and preservation of key rheological features alongside sustained drug delivery functionality. Our recent study demonstrated that nHAp can be an effective carrier for SrRan, enabling sustained *in vitro* release of biologically active Sr^{2+} and Ca^{2+} ions while contributing to bone regeneration (Stipiece et al., 2023).

The present work used SrRan-loaded nHAp (SrRan-nHAp) as a bioactive inorganic filler to develop an injectable composite hydrogel with localized drug delivery functionality. Our study was specifically focused on addressing key challenges in the preparation of composite hydrogels, such as achieving a high loading of inorganic particles while maintaining injectability and a homogeneous dispersion within the hydrogel matrix, as well as accomplishing effective chemical crosslinking, while maintaining cytocompatibility. Previously, our group has also developed HA and antimicrobial polypeptide crosslinked hydrogels (Salma-Ancane et al., 2022; Scegljovs et al., 2023) and incorporated Sr-substituted nHAp for simultaneous antibacterial activity and bone repair (Rubina et al., 2024). Despite these advances, no prior studies have reported EDC/NHS-crosslinked HA hydrogels incorporating nHAp or SrRan-nHAp for therapeutic bone regeneration. This work introduces a novel composite hydrogel system that addresses these gaps through uniform nHAp distribution, high loading capacity (up to 70 %), and systematic evaluation of the physicochemical properties and SrRan release. This injectable composite hydrogel is intended to be prepared shortly before clinical application and delivered directly into the defect site. Our findings demonstrated that EDC/NHS-crosslinked HA hydrogels incorporating nHAp or SrRan-nHAp provide tunable mechanical performance, sustained SrRan release, and excellent *in vitro* biocompatibility, offering a promising bone biomaterial for minimally invasive bone defect filling applications.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

For the synthesis of nHAp and SrRan-nHAp, the following chemicals were used: calcium carbonate (CaCO_3 , Schaefer Kalk, 99 % purity, MW 100.09 g/mol, CAS-No: 471-34-1), orthophosphoric acid (H_3PO_4 , Latvijas Ķīmija, 75 % purity, MW 97.99 g/mol, CAS-No: 7664-38-2), strontium ranelate (SrRan, Zhishang Industry Co., MW 513.49 g/mol, CAS-No: 135,459-87-9), deionized water (DI H_2O , Adrona Crystal E, 0.055 μS).

For the preparation of hydrogels, the following chemicals were used: sodium hyaluronate (Contipro Biotech, >95 % purity, MW 1.67 MDa, CAS-No: 9067-32-7), 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC, Fluorochem, 99 % purity, MW 191.70 g/mol,

CAS-No: 25,952–53–8), *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS, *Sigma Aldrich*, 98 % purity, MW 115.09 g/mol, CAS-No: 6066–82–6).

For the physicochemical characterization, the following chemicals were used: phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) tablets (pH 7.2–7.6, 1 tablet/200 mL, *Sigma Aldrich*), hyaluronidase from bovine testes (type I-S, lyophilized powder, *Sigma Aldrich*, 400–1000 units/mg solid, CAS-No: 37,326–33–3). For LC-MS analysis: acetonitrile (Supelco LiChrosolv hypergrade for LC-MS, CAS-No: 75–05–8), NH_4HCO_3 (*Sigma-Aldrich*, for LC-MS LiChropur™, CAS-Nr. 1066–33–7).

For *in vitro* cytotoxicity evaluation, the following chemicals were used: NIH/3T3 fibroblasts (ATCC®, USA), MC3T3-E1 subclone 14 pre-osteoblasts (ATCC®, USA), *Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium* (DMEM, ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA), fetal bovine serum (FBS, ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA), penicillin (*Sigma-Aldrich*, MA, USA), streptomycin (*Sigma-Aldrich*, MA, USA), Minimum Essential Medium alpha (α MEM) without ascorbic acid (*Gibco™*, *Thermo Fisher Scientific*, Waltham, MA, USA), Bio-Gide® collagen membrane (Geistlich Pharma, Wolhusen, Switzerland), phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, *Thermo Fisher Scientific*, Waltham, MA, USA), Live/Dead assay (Calcein-AM/propidium iodide, *Sigma-Aldrich*, MA, USA).

2.2. Synthesis of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles

The nHAp was chemically precipitated in a laboratory reactor (*Power Control-Visc P7*, *IKA Eurostar*, *WERKE*, Germany) following the procedure described previously by Stipniece et al. (Stipniece et al., 2023). The precipitation reaction was carried out in a 3-liter reaction vessel within a laboratory reactor equipped with an anchor stirrer to continuously stir the synthesis mixture at 100 rpm. Before the synthesis, CaCO_3 powder was calcined in a muffle furnace at 1100 °C for 1 h to obtain CaO. The calcined CaO was suspended in DI H_2O to obtain 2 L of 0.15 M $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ suspension. Then, 2 M H_3PO_4 aqueous solution was added to the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ suspension at an addition rate of 1 mL/min using an automatic dosing unit (*TITRONIC® universal*, *Schott*, Germany), reaching a Ca/P molar ratio of 1.67, corresponding to stoichiometric nHAp. The synthesis temperature was maintained at 45 °C using a laboratory hot plate with an external temperature probe (*IKA-HCT basic*, Germany). The final pH value of the suspension was ~8.5. After synthesis, the wet precipitates (suspension) were left to mature for 24 h at room temperature, vacuum filtered, and stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C for further use. Before incorporating the suspension into hydrogels, its moisture content was determined by drying at 120 °C in a moisture analyzer (*Humidity Analyzer MRS 120–3*, *Kern*, Germany). The measured moisture content of the suspension was ~80 wt %.

2.3. Synthesis of strontium ranelate-loaded hydroxyapatite nanoparticles

In this study, SrRan was used as a model drug to evaluate the drug release kinetics from the composite hydrogel matrix. The nHAp synthesis process was modified to add SrRan (10 wt %) to the nHAp particles (Stipniece et al., 2023). In the case of SrRan-containing nHAp (SrRan-nHAp), the precipitation reaction was carried out in a 600 mL beaker. First, the calcined CaO powder was dispersed in DI H_2O to obtain 200 mL of 0.5 M $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ suspension and processed using an ultrasonic processor (*UP200St*, *Hielscher*, Germany) equipped with a sonotrode (*S26d2*, *Hielscher*, Germany) at 26 kHz pulsed frequency for three 15 s cycles with 15 s breaks in between. The suspension was then heated to 35 °C using a laboratory hot plate (*MSH-300i*, *Biosan*, Latvia) with an external temperature probe under continuous mechanical stirring (*MM-1000*, *Biosan*, Latvia) at 400 rpm. The SrRan powder was dissolved in a 2 M H_3PO_4 aqueous solution (100 mg/mL) using an ultrasonic bath for 10 min. Then, the SrRan- H_3PO_4 solution was gradually (approximately 1 mL/min) added using a measuring pipette to the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ suspension until the pH reached ~8.5. After synthesis, the wet precipitates (suspension) were left to mature for 24 h at room temperature, vacuum filtered, and stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C for further

use. Before incorporating the suspension into hydrogels, its moisture content was determined by drying at 120 °C in a moisture analyzer (*Humidity Analyzer MRS 120–3*, *Kern*, Germany). The measured moisture content of the suspension was ~80 wt %.

2.4. Synthesis of hydrogels

The hydrogels were chemically crosslinked using EDC/NHS (Fig. 1).

The designation and composition of the fabricated hydrogels are summarized in Table 1.

The schematic hydrogel fabrication process is shown in Fig. 2. The components were mixed using two interconnected syringes (*Fisher Scientific*, *BD PlastiPak™* Syringe with *Luer Lock*, 5 mL) at room temperature. First, a HA solution was prepared by mixing 0.21 g of HA and 2 mL of DI H_2O 40 times in two connected syringes. The prepared HA solution was left in a fridge at 4 °C for 24 h for complete dissolution. Afterwards, the HA solution was pre-activated by adding 0.186 g EDC and mixing 40 times, then adding 0.112 g NHS and mixing 40 times.

The nHAp and SrRan-nHAp suspensions were weighed into syringes to fabricate composite hydrogels. The amount of suspension needed to prepare hydrogels was calculated based on the required weight % of nHAp or SrRan-nHAp in each hydrogel series, as well as the moisture content of the suspension. The HA/nHAp and HA/SrRan-nHAp composite hydrogels were synthesized by mixing 2 mL of the pre-activated HA gel and the nHAp or SrRan-nHAp suspension using two connected syringes ~100 times.

Overall, three different forms of the hydrogels were tested – as-prepared, moulded, and lyophilized. As-prepared hydrogels are the components mixed in two connected syringes, and used immediately after hydrogel synthesis. Moulded hydrogels are as-prepared hydrogels extruded into custom-made 3D moulds ($\varnothing = 10$ mm, $h = 5$ mm) and kept at room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) for 24 h to crosslink. Lyophilized hydrogels are moulded hydrogels removed from the moulds, frozen at -26 °C, and lyophilized in a lyophilizer (*BETA 2–8 LSCplus*, *Martin Christ*, Germany) at 75 mtorr, -85 °C for 72 h.

At least three replicates from different batches were analyzed in each test to ensure reproducibility and consistency.

2.5. Physicochemical characterization

2.5.1. Phase composition

To analyse the phase composition of the lyophilized nHAp and SrRan-nHAp powders and the lyophilized hydrogels, X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD, PANalytical AERIS, *Panalytical*, Almelo, Netherlands) was used with Cu $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation produced at 40 kV and 30 mA (Fig. S1A). Diffraction data were collected in a 10 – 70° 2θ range, with a step size of 0.05° 2θ and time per step of 2.5 s. The phase in the recorded diffraction patterns was identified using a PANalytical X-Pert Highscore 2.2 software (*Panalytical*, Almelo, Netherlands). The International Centre for Diffraction Data PDF-2 (ICDD, Newtown Square, Pennsylvania, USA) database was used to analyse the obtained data. Normalization was performed by setting the range 0 to 1, where 0 was assigned to the minimum and 1 to the maximum values of raw diffraction intensities of all samples.

2.5.2. Molecular structure

To analyse the functional groups of the lyophilized nHAp and SrRan-nHAp powders and the lyophilized hydrogels, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR, *Nicolet IS50 FT-IR*, *Thermo Fisher*, USA) in the attenuated reflectance mode (ATR, *ISSO ATR Nicolet*, *Thermo Fisher*, USA) was used (Fig. S1 B). For spectra collection, samples were ground into a fine powder using a Mini-Mill PULVERISETTE 23 (*FRITCH*, *Idar-Oberstein*, Germany) ball mill. Absorbance was measured in the wavenumber range of 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} and at 4 cm^{-1} resolution, 64 scans per sample. Background spectrum with no sample in the infrared beam was acquired and subtracted from the sample spectrum. The obtained

Fig. 1. The crosslinking mechanism of HA using EDC and NHS crosslinkers.

Table 1

Designation and composition of the fabricated hydrogels.

Designation	Inorganic component	HA: inorganic component ratio, wt %	EDC:NHS molar ratio	HA polymer chains, μmol	EDC:HA repeat unit ratio	Total water volume, mL
0 % nHAp	nHAp	100:0	1:1	0.126	1.85:1	4
30 % nHAp		70:30				
40 % nHAp		60:40				
50 % nHAp		50:50				
60 % nHAp		40:60				
70 % nHAp		30:70				
30 % SrRan-nHAp	SrRan-nHAp	70:30				
50 % SrRan-nHAp		50:50				
70 % SrRan-nHAp		30:70				

spectra were normalized using the Origin 2020 v9.0 software algorithm. Normalization was performed by setting the range 0 to 1, where 0 was assigned to the minimum and 1 to the maximum values of raw absorbance intensities of all samples.

2.5.3. Morphology

The surface and cross-section morphology of the lyophilized hydrogel samples (Fig. S2) was visualized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) Verios 5 XHR (Thermo Scientific, USA). The samples were sputtered with 15 pulsations (15 nm-carbon layer using a Leica EM ACE200 (Leica Microsystems, Germany), attached to an aluminium sample holder with electrically conductive double-sided adhesive carbon tape. Secondary electrons were recorded at an accelerating voltage of 2 kV to produce images.

2.5.4. Microstructure

Microstructure of the lyophilized hydrogels (Fig. S3) was analysed using micro-computed tomography (μCT ; $\mu\text{CT}50$, Scanco Medical AG, Switzerland). Scanning was performed using an energy of 55 kVp, a current of 109 μA , and a pixel size of 4 μm . Each sample was scanned for

approximately 5 h. After scanning, a 3D image was extracted from the μCT projection data.

2.5.5. Swelling degree, gel fraction and stability

To evaluate the swelling degree of the moulded hydrogels, the pre-weighed hydrogel samples were immersed in 20 mL of DI H_2O at 37 $^\circ\text{C}$ at 100 rpm. The swollen samples were weighed at different intervals: 30 min, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 h, 1, 2, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days. The swelling degree was calculated using Eq. (1):

$$\text{Swelling degree}(\%) = (W_s - W_0)/W_0 * 100\% \quad (1)$$

where W_s is the weight of the swollen sample (g), and W_0 is the initial weight of the sample (g).

To determine the gel fraction of the hydrogels, lyophilized hydrogel samples were weighed, placed in 200 mL of DI H_2O , and placed in an incubator-shaker (ES-20, Biosan, Latvia) at 37 $^\circ\text{C}$, 100 rpm to extract the un-crosslinked polymer. After 48 h, the water was decanted and the samples were frozen at -26 $^\circ\text{C}$, lyophilized at -85 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 72 h, and weighed. The gel fraction was calculated using Eq. (2):

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the hydrogel fabrication process, a) HA crosslinking, b) synthesis of nHAp or SrRan-nHAp, c) preparation of HA, HA/nHAp, and HA/SrRan-nHAp hydrogels.

$$\text{Gel fraction}(\%) = W_E/W_0 * 100\% \quad (2)$$

where W_E is the weight of the extracted sample at each time point (g), and W_0 is the initial weight of the sample (g).

Additionally, hydrogel long-term stability was assessed (Fig. S4). Briefly, composite hydrogels were lyophilized, weighed, and placed in a phosphate-buffered saline solution (PBS, pH = 7.4) at 37 °C at 100 rpm. At determined time points (6 h, 1, 7, 14, 28, and 56 days), the samples were withdrawn from the degradation medium, frozen at -26 °C, lyophilized, and weighed. The remaining weight of the composite hydrogels was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Weight}\% = W_D/W_0 * 100\%, \quad (3)$$

where W_D is the weight of the lyophilized sample at a certain time point in the stability study, and W_0 is the initial weight of the dry sample, g.

Three replicate samples from different hydrogel batches were analysed to evaluate swelling degree, gel fraction and stability, and the results were presented as an average value of the three replicates \pm standard deviation.

2.5.6. Enzymatic degradation

For enzymatic degradation studies, the moulded HA hydrogels containing 0 % nHAp, 50 % nHAp, and 50 % SrRan-nHAp were placed in

containers containing 10 mL DI H₂O and 400 U hyaluronidase and incubated at 37 °C at 100 rpm until complete dissolution of the sample. At determined time points (24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 h), the samples were taken out of the degradation medium and weighed. The degree of enzymatic degradation was calculated using Eq. (3):

$$\text{Weight}\% = W_{DE}/W_{0E} * 100\%, \quad (4)$$

where W_{DE} is the weight of the sample after enzymatic degradation (g), and W_{0E} is the initial weight of the sample (g). All results were estimated from the data of three individual experiments, and all data were expressed as the mean value \pm standard deviation.

The enzymatic degradation products of the composite hydrogel were analysed by liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS).

2.5.6.1. analysis of enzymatic degradation products. Liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS) analysis was carried out to determine the enzymatic degradation products of the HA and 50 % nHAp hydrogels using a Vanquish Core (Thermo Scientific, USA) HPLC system coupled to an Orbitrap Exploris 120 (Thermo Scientific, USA) high-resolution mass spectrometer. The chromatographic separation was carried out on an Atlantis Premier BEH Z-HILIC 1.7 μ m, VanGuard Fit 2.1 \times 100 mm column (Waters, UK) with an ACQUITY UPLC BEH Z-HILIC 1.7 μ m, VanGuard 2.1 \times 5 mm pre-column (Waters, UK). Column temperature was set at 40 °C,

and the mobile phase flow rate was 0.4 ml/min. The mobile phase A was a 15 mM NH_4HCO_3 solution in water with pH 9.0, and the mobile phase B was 90 % acetonitrile with 15 mM NH_4HCO_3 , pH 9.0. The gradient elution was employed, with the mobile phase B held at 90 % for 5 min, decreasing to 65 % between 5 and 6 min, and returning to 90 % between 6.5 and 12 min. The injection volume was 2 μL . For mass spectrometry, the electrospray ionisation source (ESI) was operated in negative mode, the detection was performed in Full Scan mode set to mass range from 75 to 850 m/z , and the mass resolution was set to 30,000. The spray voltage was set to 2900 V, with an evaporation temperature of 350 °C. The total analysis time was 12 min. TraceFinder 5.1 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) software was used for data processing.

2.5.7. Strontium ranelate release

Moulded HA hydrogels containing 30 wt %, 50 wt %, and 70 wt % SrRan-nHAp were used for the SrRan release kinetics assessment. A control group of HA/nHAp composite hydrogels containing 50 wt % nHAp was employed. For each series, five samples were tested. The samples were placed in a sterile plastic container with 20 mL of PBS solution and placed in an incubator-shaker at 37 °C and 100 rpm. 2 mL aliquots were collected from each sample at the designated time intervals (30 min, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 24, 48, 72 h, 7, 14, 30, 42, and 56 d). The volume removed was then replenished with 2 mL of a fresh PBS solution.

The absorbance of the standard solutions and samples was measured against PBS solution in a two-beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Evolution 300, Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) at a wavelength of $\lambda = 318$ nm. First, a five-point calibration curve was constructed over the SrRan concentration range 10 – 70 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The equation of the obtained calibration curve was $y = 0.0249x + 0.0069$ and had a determination coefficient $R^2 = 1$. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) of SrRan were calculated using results obtained from the calibration curve using Eqs. (4) and 5:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3\sigma/B \quad (4)$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10\sigma/B, \quad (5)$$

where σ – standard deviation of y-intercepts from the calibration curve regression line, and B – slope of the trendline of the calibration curve. The calculated LOD was equal to 0.18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and the LOQ was 0.53 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

2.5.8. Rheology

A Discovery series HR20 rheometer (TA Instruments, DE, USA) was used to characterize the rheological properties of composite hydrogels. Parallel upper plate geometry with a 25 mm diameter was used, and the gap size was set at 1000 μm . The sample diameter was equal to the geometric diameter. Before taking all measurements, all samples were equilibrated for 180 s. Silicon oil was spread around the sample before the measurements to avoid sample evaporation and drying.

As-prepared hydrogels were extruded on the Peltier plate for the gelation time test. The analysis was performed for 4.3 h, at 0.2 % strain and 1 Hz frequency until complete crosslinking (storage modulus G' reaches a plateau).

For the amplitude sweep, frequency sweep, and compression tests, the as-prepared hydrogels were extruded into custom-made molds (diameter 25 mm, height 1 mm) and allowed to partially crosslink at room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) for ~ 1 min before testing. This short hold time enabled initial rheological properties post-extrusion assessment, with full gelation requiring 2–4 h (see Section 3.4).

The amplitude sweep test was performed in an oscillation mode at 25 °C within a shear strain range from 0.01 to 1000 %, at a constant frequency of 1 Hz. A frequency sweep test was performed at 25 °C and a frequency range from 0.01 to 100 Hz at a constant 0.2 % strain, obtained from a previously determined linear viscoelastic region (LVR) during the amplitude sweep test.

The compression tests were conducted in the frequency range of 0.01 to 16 Hz, with an axial displacement of 30 μm , an 8 N axial force (axial force > dynamic force = 30 %), and compression storage modulus (E') and compression loss modulus (E'') were monitored. The hydrogels' molecular weight between crosslinks (M_c) was calculated using Eq. (6):

$$M_c = RTd/G', \quad (6)$$

where R is the universal gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, d is the polymer density, and G' is the storage modulus at 1 Hz frequency. The crosslinking density (q) was then calculated using Eq. (7):

$$q = Mw/M_c, \quad (7)$$

where Mw is the monomer's molecular weight (Quantify Polymer Crosslinking Density Using Rheology & DMA, n.d.).

2.5.9. Injectability

The injectability of the hydrogels was determined by measuring injection force, viscosity recovery after simulated injection (structural integrity), and viscosity dependence on shear rate (pseudoplastic behaviour).

The injection force was measured using an electromechanical universal testing machine (Model 25ST, Tinius Olsen, USA). The 5 mL syringe (the inner diameter of the tip was 1.8 mm) without a needle containing the hydrogel was put in a custom-made holder (Rubina et al., 2024). The hydrogel was extruded out of the syringe at a speed of 2 mm/s in compression mode, and the force applied (the injection force) was registered. Four measurements were carried out in parallel for each series of the hydrogels. Measurements were taken immediately after synthesis.

The viscosity recovery after simulated injection was measured using the rheometer. The as-prepared hydrogels were extruded into custom-made moulds (diameter 25 mm, height 1 mm) and kept at room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) for 1 min to crosslink. A cyclic strain time sweep test was performed to gain insights into the structural integrity of the hydrogels. In this test, the viscosity was plotted as a function of time at alternating high and low shear rates (3 intervals: 0.1, 150, and 0.1 s^{-1}) at 25 °C. The viscosity recovery was calculated for each sample by setting the average viscosity value in interval 1 at 100 % and comparing it with the average viscosity value in interval 3.

The viscosity-shear rate tests were performed on a rheometer at logarithmically increasing shear rate values from 0.1 to 500 s^{-1} , at 25 °C. Viscosity dependence on shear rate was monitored.

2.6. In vitro cytocompatibility

For the direct contact assay, the as-prepared hydrogels were extruded into custom-made moulds (diameter 25 mm, height 1 mm) and kept at room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) for 24 h to crosslink. For the leachables assay, the as-prepared hydrogels were extruded into a 96-well plate (diameter 5 mm, height ~ 1 mm) and kept at room temperature (21 ± 2 °C) for 24 h to fully crosslink. The hydrogels were steam sterilized at 105 °C for 4 min under 131 kPa using a tabletop pre-vacuum autoclave (CertoClav Vacuum Pro 22, Austria). The sterile hydrogel samples were refrigerated at 4 °C until further use.

2.6.1. Cell culture

NIH/3T3 fibroblasts and MC3T3-E1 subclone 14 preosteoblasts were seeded at a density of 10,000 cells per well in 96-well plates. NIH/3T3 cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium supplemented with 10 % (v/v) fetal bovine serum, 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ penicillin, and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ streptomycin. MC3T3-E1 cells were cultured in Minimum Essential Medium alpha (α MEM) without ascorbic acid, supplemented with 10 % (v/v) FBS, 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ penicillin, and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ streptomycin. All cultures were incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5 % CO_2 .

2.6.2. Leachables test

Materials and the negative control (Bio-Gide® collagen membrane) were pre-soaked in PBS for 24 h at 37 °C. The PBS was aspirated, and materials were then incubated for an additional 24 h in DMEM (for NIH/3T3) or α MEM (for MC3T3-E1). Resulting extracts were filtered through 0.2 μ m membranes, neutralized to pH 7.4, and supplemented with FBS to a final concentration of 10 % (v/v). After a 24-hour incubation of cells with 100 μ L of extract medium, biocompatibility was assessed using a Live/Dead assay (calcein-AM/propidium iodide).

2.6.3. Direct contact test

Hydrogels were cut into ~5–10 mm² pieces and placed directly on preformed cell layers in complete growth medium. After 24 h of incubation, materials were removed, cells were gently washed with PBS, and viability was assessed using the same Live/Dead assay.

2.7. Statistical analysis

All data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) from at least three independent samples. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). For physicochemical data, Tukey's post hoc test was applied, while *in vitro* cytocompatibility results were evaluated using Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$ ($p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.001$; *** $p < 0.0001$). Only significant differences are indicated, whereas non-significant comparisons are omitted for clarity.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Swelling and gel fraction

From the plots obtained (Fig. 3A), the swelling degree decreases with

increasing weight fraction of nHAp in the composite hydrogel. The swelling degree of the composite hydrogels after 7 days was 1542 \pm 72 % for the 0 % nHAp, 534 \pm 36 % for the 30 % nHAp, 347 \pm 83 % for the 40 % nHAp, 368 \pm 6 % for the 50 % nHAp, 240 \pm 30 % for the 60 % nHAp, and 269 \pm 27 % for the 70 % nHAp composite hydrogel.

This tendency can be explained by the effect nHAp has on the microstructure of the hydrogels. The swelling capacity of the composite hydrogels is determined by the porosity of the hydrogel, as well as the polar [OH] and [COOH] functional groups in the HA structure, which actively bind water molecules (Vakili et al., 2025). In the presence of nHAp, the oxygen atoms of the carboxylic and amide groups in HA form coordination complexes with Ca²⁺ from nHAp (Fig. 3D) (Giubertoni et al., 2021), bringing the polymer chains closer together, increasing the crosslinking density and thereby reducing the swelling ability of the hydrogel (Kesharwani et al., 2021). A similar relationship was observed in another study, where the addition of the nHAp phase contributed to a decrease in the swelling of HA-gelatin composite hydrogels (Zhao et al., 2022).

This hypothesis was tested by gel fraction analysis of HA hydrogels and HA/nHAp composite hydrogels. The gel fraction of HA/nHAp composite hydrogels increased with higher nHAp content (Fig. 3B). Hydrogels with 70 % nHAp showed the highest gel fraction (75 \pm 1 %) but reduced swelling (269 \pm 27 %). This aligns with previous findings by Rubina et al. (Rubina et al., 2024) and Svarca et al. (Svarca et al., 2022). According to the swelling ratio and gel fraction analysis, incorporating the nHAp phase into the chemically crosslinked hydrogel network improves the structural integrity and mechanical strength, as reported in (Mihajlovic et al., 2021).

3.2. In vitro enzymatic degradation

A qualitative hydrogel enzymatic degradation test was conducted to

Fig. 3. Swelling degree (A), gel fraction (B), enzymatic degradation (C), of HA hydrogels and HA/nHAp composite hydrogels, and possible Ca²⁺ ion complexation with HA moieties (D). (* - for $p < 0.05$; ** - for $p < 0.01$; *** - for $p < 0.001$; **** - for $p < 0.0001$, $n = 3$).

demonstrate that the activity of the enzyme hyaluronidase breaks down the glycosidic bonds of HA (Patil et al., 2023) and completely dissolves the hydrogel. According to the obtained results (Fig. 3C), hydrogels without nHAp and composite hydrogels with 30 % nHAp fully dissolve within the first 24 h, whereas composite hydrogels with higher amounts of nHAp fully degrade within two to five days. This could be explained by the dissolution of nHAp, which is associated with a local pH increase. Studies show that even a slight increase in the pH can enhance the hydrogels' stability, prolonging the degradation time (Rubina et al., 2024). The hindering effect of nHAp presence on the degradation of composite hydrogels can also be observed in the long-term stability results (Fig. S4). The addition of nHAp to the hydrogel can reduce the degradation of the hydrogel by up to 20 %. It can be concluded that the hyaluronidase enzyme present in the human body can completely dissolve HA hydrogels and HA/nHAp composite hydrogels, which means these materials are bioresorbable. The enzymatic degradation products were further analysed by liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry.

3.2.1. Mass spectrometry analysis of enzymatic hydrogel degradation products

LC-MS was performed on enzymatically degraded HA (0 % nHAp) and HA/nHAp (50 % nHAp) hydrogels to identify the main degradation products (Table 2). SrRan containing hydrogels were not analysed as hyaluronidase-driven degradation is determined primarily by the HA matrix. The main degradation products were low molecular weight HA oligomers, predominantly disaccharides (~88–89 wt %), corresponding to the repeating dimeric unit of HA. Minor amounts of monosaccharides (~4–6 wt %), trimers (~2–3 wt %), and tetramers (~3–5 wt %) were also detected.

The findings are consistent with previous reports that hyaluronidase degrades HA into short-chain oligomers. The degradation products and their amounts mediated by the enzymatic degradation of HA and HA/nHAp hydrogels correspond to short-chain HA oligomers (Table 2). HA oligomers are biologically active molecules that influence tissue repair processes, including increased fibroplasia, collagen deposition, and neovascularization. HA fragments with the range of 3 to 25 disaccharides have been shown to stimulate angiogenesis, fibroblast proliferation, and ECM deposition, thereby enabling wound and bone healing (Mast et al., 1995; Silva et al., 2016; West et al., 1985; Zhang et al., 2024). Specifically, fibroplasia contributes to early bone defect healing by producing collagen and ECM, which form a fibrous tissue scaffold for callus formation (H. Wang et al., 2024). Collagen, as the main organic component of bone, provides the framework for mineral deposition and enhances mechanical integrity (Lin et al., 2020; Selvaraj et al., 2024). Furthermore, neovascularization is critical for nutrient delivery, waste removal, and recruitment of osteoprogenitor cells to the repair area (Li et al., 2025; Zhou et al., 2022). These findings indicate that enzymatic degradation of the HA and HA/nHAp hydrogels under physiologically relevant conditions enables resorption and generates bioactive HA fragments that can positively impact bone tissue regeneration.

Table 2
Weight percentages of enzymatic degradation products detected by LC-MS in HA hydrogels and HA/nHAp composite hydrogels.

Sample	Amount of the HA degradation product			
	Disaccharides, wt %	Monosaccharides, wt %	Trimer, wt %	Tetramer, wt %
HA (0 % nHAp)	89.0	6.4	1.9	2.8
HA/nHAp (50 % nHAp)	88.3	4.5	2.7	4.6

3.3. SrRan release

SrRan release kinetics analysis was performed for 8 weeks (56 days) for 3 series of composite hydrogels: 30 % SrRan-nHAp, 50 % SrRan-nHAp, and 70 % SrRan-nHAp (Fig. 4).

HAp nanoparticles demonstrate a high affinity toward hydrophilic drugs, therefore SrRan molecules can be electrostatically adsorbed on the highly charged surface of nHAp (Stipniec et al., 2023). The initial SrRan release depends on the strength of this electrostatic interaction. Furthermore, the SrRan-nHAp particles are uniformly dispersed within the hydrogel matrix, providing physical entrapment of the drug within the composite hydrogel. Once released from the nanoparticle surface, SrRan must diffuse through the porous, chemically crosslinked HA matrix. The crosslinking density and pore size of the hydrogel regulate how quickly molecules can migrate out, providing a secondary level of control. Adding HAp to the hydrogel also influences its stiffness and gel fraction, which can slow down matrix degradation and thus prolong drug release (Jung et al., 2021; Ugrinovic et al., 2024). Within the first 6 h, 61–68 % of SrRan was rapidly released. The initial burst release profile (first 6 h) suggests diffusion-controlled kinetics (e.g., Higuchi model), as cumulative release was non-linear with time (Loca et al., 2018). After 24 h, $928 \pm 22 \mu\text{g}$ ($66 \pm 3 \%$) of SrRan were released from 30 % SrRan-nHAp, $2643 \pm 228 \mu\text{g}$ ($73 \pm 5 \%$) from 50 % SrRan-nHAp, and $7165 \pm 29 \mu\text{g}$ ($79 \pm 2 \%$) from 70 % SrRan-nHAp composite hydrogels. After 56 days, $999 \pm 37 \mu\text{g}$ ($71 \pm 5 \%$), $2700 \pm 223 \mu\text{g}$ ($75 \pm 4 \%$), and $7420 \pm 61 \mu\text{g}$ ($82 \pm 2 \%$) of SrRan were released from the 30 % SrRan-nHAp, 50 % SrRan-nHAp and 70 % SrRan-nHAp composite hydrogels, respectively. Thus, composite hydrogels with higher SrRan-nHAp wt % provide a higher amount of SrRan released into the PBS medium. This biphasic profile is attributed to electrostatically adsorbed SrRan molecules on nHAp crystallite surfaces, rapidly releasing in a burst phase, as evidenced by unchanged XRD patterns and preserved FTIR bands (Fig. S1, B), consistent with our prior characterisation with UV-Vis and ICP-MS data on SrRan-nHAp (Stipniec et al., 2023).

Various studies indicate that a SrRan burst release within the first 24 h can stimulate early osteoblast differentiation (Chiang et al., 2021; Svarca et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022). For example, our previous study (Stipniec et al., 2023) confirmed that SrRan burst release in DMEM from SrRan-nHAp (10wt % SrRan) nanoparticles (65 % SrRan released in 24 h) leads to increased alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity and enhanced expression of collagen I and osteocalcin in preosteoblasts and osteoblasts, indicating stimulation of early osteoblast differentiation and bone formation.

3.4. Rheological characterization

Rheology tests were carried out to assess the viscoelastic properties of the hydrogels (Fig. 5, A-F). In the amplitude sweep test (Fig. 5A), it was observed that all series of chemically crosslinked hydrogels showed gel-like behaviour, as the storage modulus (G') was significantly higher than the loss modulus (G'') ($G' > G''$). The amplitude sweep test showed a distinct LVR in which the moduli of G' and G'' remained constant regardless of the increase in strain. The LVR is exhibited up to a strain of $\epsilon \approx 12 \%$ for all hydrogel series. Continued deformation of the samples reached the crossover point ($G' = G''$), indicating the strain at which the material starts to behave like a liquid.

After determining the LVR in the amplitude sweep test, a frequency sweep test was performed at 0.2 % shear strain (Fig. 5B). The hydrogels showed a relatively rapid increase in storage modulus (G') until the frequency reached 32 Hz. A similar trend was observed for HA biopolymer solutions/hydrogels (Park et al., 2022). The subsequent rapid decrease of the G'' modulus at frequencies higher than 56 Hz could be due to sample breakage or a limitation of the system measurement, since the measurement range of G'' is not the same as that of G' .

Compression tests were performed to simulate the human body's

Fig. 4. Cumulative SrRan release from the composite hydrogels after 24 h (A) and 56 days (B) ($n = 5$).

physiological conditions and investigate the viscoelastic properties of the composite hydrogels under such conditions. The dependence of the compression storage (E') and compression loss (E'') moduli as a function of frequency under constant axial force compression was tested for all prepared compositions. (Fig. 5C). The slightly higher values of E' and E'' in hydrogels with higher nHAp content can be related to a higher resistance to lateral propagation due to the physical bonds formed between nHAp particles and HA molecules (Fig. 3D). The E' and E'' curves did not cross in the whole frequency range, indicating the stability and strength of the chemically crosslinked polymer network (Baniasadi et al., 2015).

Furthermore, the compression storage moduli (E') are plotted as a function of crosslinking density (q) (Fig. 5D). The E' increased with the q , which is higher for composite hydrogels with a higher nHAp content. A higher crosslinking density leads to a lower swelling degree and polymer chain flexibility. Moreover, these results show that the addition of nHAp can increase the crosslinking density of the composite hydrogels through forming the electrostatic bonds between COO^- and $\text{CH}_3\text{-CO-NH}_2$ functional groups of HA and with Ca^{2+} of nHAp (Farbod et al., 2014), enhancing the stiffness of the hydrogel.

The stiffness of the hydrogels – G' at 1 Hz and 0.2 % strain – was determined from the amplitude sweep test results (Fig. 5E). This approach to stiffness determination has been used for both chemically and physically crosslinked hydrogels (Salma-Ancane et al., 2022). The results show that increasing composite hydrogel nHAp content from 10 to 70 wt % increases the stiffness from 1.5 to 2.8 kPa (Fig. 5E). Stiffness in this low kPa range corresponds to clinically relevant injectable bone-repair hydrogels, which must be extrudable by syringe yet provide sufficient mechanical support after injection. Hydrogels with tunable stiffness between ~ 1 kPa and 10 kPa have been reported to promote MSC proliferation, spreading and osteogenic differentiation (Fouladgar et al., 2025; Guvendiren & Burdick, 2012; Luo et al., 2022). The measured stiffness of 1.5 to 2.8 kPa, therefore, falls within the osteoconductive mechanical window known to support early bone-related cellular activities while maintaining injectability. This mechanical profile is expected to support cell-matrix interactions, promote osteogenic differentiation, and enhance bone tissue formation.

The gelation time (Fig. 5F) was measured to determine how long it takes for the hydrogel to fully crosslink (reach the plateau of the storage modulus G'). Hydrogels without nHAp reached full gelation within approximately 2 h, whereas nHAp-containing composite hydrogels required 3 to 4 h to crosslink completely. This *in situ* gelation within ≤ 4 h corresponds to the clinically acceptable window for injectable bone fillers, allowing sufficient handling time for surgical manipulation and controlled filling of irregular bone defects, while avoiding premature

solidifying in the syringe or excessive delay of setting *in vivo* (Correa et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2017). The hydrogels have high viscosity at rest but flow easily during injection, i.e., they are shear-thinning balancing injectability and retention.

3.5. Injectability

To inject the hydrogels, it is necessary to deliver the resulting gel to the target site using an injection device, i.e., a syringe. It is therefore essential to know how much force must be applied to displace the hydrogel at a given injection rate. As already mentioned, composite hydrogels are designed to replicate the composition of bone, i.e., polymer phase with nanoparticles of inorganic phase, and to promote bone regeneration. Thus, incorporating the inorganic nHAp phase into HA hydrogels was expected to affect the injection strength due to the change in viscous properties. Therefore, the injection force was measured for each series of samples to determine the appropriate amount of nHAp without deteriorating the injectability of the composite hydrogels. The injectability of the hydrogels is summarised in Fig. 6A.

The injection force of the hydrogels immediately after synthesis (Fig. 6A) is up to 2.5 N. The clinically accepted maximum manual injection force is 30 N (Maria Alonso et al., 2021; Rubina et al., 2024), and biomaterials can be considered easily injectable if the injection force does not exceed 12 N (Day & Boccaccini, 2005). Therefore, the composite hydrogels can be considered easily manually injectable. Adding the nHAp phase in HA hydrogels increases their injection force due to additional physical crosslinking between HA's negatively charged carboxylic groups and the positively charged calcium ions of nHAp.

Cyclic strain time sweep tests were conducted to determine whether the resulting hydrogels could recover their viscosity after applying the injection force (Fig. 6B,C). This property of hydrogels is important as it provides the necessary support and stability at the bone defect site and controlled release of the incorporated drugs (Vallmajo-Martin et al., 2024).

The results show that all hydrogels had viscosity recovery rates in the range 74–89 %. The composite hydrogels developed can withstand the stress applied during injection and recover their viscosity. The 60 % nHAp and 70 % nHAp composite hydrogels showed the lowest recovery, i.e., 78 ± 15 % and 74 ± 5 %, respectively. This could be because the hydrogel needs more time to recover its chemical crosslinks and viscosity if its matrix is composed mainly of inorganic nHAp. The statistical analysis of the results showed no statistical difference between all series of hydrogels.

Shear rate-dependent viscosity tests were carried out to assess the ability of the samples to decrease in viscosity (flow) when the shear rate

Fig. 5. Oscillatory rheology of the HA hydrogels and the HA/nHAp composite hydrogels: (A) amplitude sweep test obtained at 1 Hz frequency; (B) frequency sweep test obtained at 0.2 % strain; (C) compression curves, and (D) correlation between compression storage moduli (E') (extracted from compression curves at 1 Hz) and calculated crosslinking density values, (E) hydrogel stiffness (storage modulus, G') at 1 Hz and 0.2 % strain obtained from amplitude sweep tests, (F) hydrogel gelation time (* - for $p < 0.05$; ** - for $p < 0.01$; *** - for $p < 0.001$; **** - for $p < 0.0001$, $n = 3$).

is increased. The results are presented in Fig. 6D For all composite hydrogel series, the viscosity decreases rapidly with increasing shear rate. These results correlate with the injectability and cyclic viscosity recovery tests and indicate that the composite hydrogels possess shear-thinning properties.

Overall, the injectability tests demonstrated that both HA hydrogels and HA-nHAp composite hydrogels required a very low injection force (1.5–2.5 N) immediately after synthesis, confirming their suitability for manual syringe delivery. In addition, all hydrogels exhibited shear-thinning behaviour and rapid viscosity recovery (74–89 %) after

simulated injection, indicating good structural resilience and stability at the defect site.

To better contextualize these results, Table 3 summarizes the comparative performance and functional advantages of the developed HA/nHAp composite hydrogels relative to representative injectable hydrogel systems, focusing on mechanical strength, injectability, degradation, and drug release performance.

The comparison highlights that most reported injectable hydrogels lack quantitative data on injection force, an essential parameter for clinical injectability. The developed HA/nHAp composite hydrogels

Fig. 6. The HA hydrogel and the HA/nHAp composite hydrogel injection force (A) ($n = 4$), viscosity recovery test graphical representation (B) ($n = 3$), calculated viscosity recovery after simulated injection (C) ($n = 3$), and viscosity depending on shear rate (D) ($n = 3$) (* - for $p < 0.05$; ** - for $p < 0.01$; *** - for $p < 0.001$; **** - for $p < 0.0001$).

Table 3

Comparative performance and functional advantages of the developed HA/nHAp composite hydrogel over representative injectable hydrogel systems.

Material	Mechanical strength/stiffness	Injectability	Degradation	Drug release performance	Reference
HA/nHAp composite (70 % nHAp or SrRan-nHAp)	Stiffness 2.8 kPa	Shear-thinning, injection force 2.5 N	Fully degradable by hyaluronidase enzyme	Controlled release of SrRan from 70 % SrRan-nHAp for 56 days. 79 % released within first 24 h.	The present work
Gellan Gum/Elastin + ZnO and β -TCP	Stiffness 0.6 - 2 kPa (pre-crosslinking)	Shear-thinning, injection force not studied	20 % weight loss after 7 days in DPBS	Not studied	Barberi et al., 2025
HA/RGD peptide + aspirin and BMSCs	Stiffness 0.131 kPa before UV crosslinking, 1 kPa after UV crosslinking	Shear-thinning, injection force not studied	~60 % weight loss after 40 days in PBS	Aspirin - 20 % released in first 24 h, 80 % released in 7 days.	Guo et al., 2024
Gelatin/HA + nHAp + MSCs	Stiffness 0.8 kPa	Extruded through 27-gauge needle, injection force not studied	~50 % weight loss after 3 days in PBS	Not studied	Lee et al., 2024
Chitosan/cellulose + curcumin-loaded PCL microspheres	Young's modulus 2.03 - 4.53 kPa	Not studied	55 - 84 % weight loss after 30 days in PBS	~23 - 35 % drug released in 7 days	Kalantarnia et al., 2025

demonstrate higher stiffness (up to 2.8 kPa) within the osteoconductive range, documented enzymatic degradability, and quantitatively characterized drug-release kinetics, features rarely evaluated in previous systems. The inclusion of enzyme-mediated degradation studies provides a more realistic assessment of biodegradation, a critical

requirement for bone-repair biomaterials. Furthermore, injectable hydrogel systems are rarely loaded with therapeutic agents, and their drug release profiles are often insufficiently characterised. These results underline the translational potential of the developed composite hydrogels, which combine clinically compatible injectability, controlled

degradation, and sustained drug release within a single multifunctional platform.

3.6. *In vitro* biocompatibility

The hydrogel and composite hydrogel *in vitro* biocompatibility results are summarized in Fig. 7.

According to ISO 10,993–5, a reduction in cell viability by >30 % is considered a cytotoxic effect. The *in vitro* test results (Fig. 7, A–D) clearly show that cell viability reduction in all tested hydrogel series was below the 30 % threshold (cell viability was above 70 %). Therefore, in accordance with ISO 10,993–5, the tested materials are considered non-cytotoxic. Similar results have been obtained in other studies on HA-based hydrogels for clinical applications (Han et al., 2020; Øvrebo et al., 2024; Samanta et al., 2022), further supporting HA as an outstanding material for developing hydrogels for tissue regeneration. Furthermore, incorporation of nHAp particles generates a roughened inner surface within the hydrogel network (Fig. S2), which may contribute to cell attachment and osteoconductivity (Sun et al., 2022; Huang & Chu, 2019). However, it should be noted that SEM imaging was done on lyophilized hydrogel samples, and as-prepared hydrogels might reveal a smoother surface. To confirm the effect of nHAp incorporation on cell attachment and osteoconductivity, further *in vitro* studies should be conducted.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we developed EDC/NHS-crosslinked hyaluronic acid (HA) injectable hydrogels incorporating hydroxyapatite nanoparticles (nHAp) or strontium ranelate-loaded hydroxyapatite nanoparticles (SrRan-nHAp), designed as multifunctional platforms for bone defect filling. The composite hydrogels exhibited the essential properties required for injectable bone repair applications, including manual injectability, bioresorbability, cytocompatibility, tunable stiffness, and drug delivery capacity.

Incorporation of nHAp significantly enhanced the mechanical performance of the HA hydrogels by increasing stiffness and gel fraction while prolonging enzymatic degradation. Given the intrinsic biocompatibility and bioactivity of hydroxyapatite, these modifications are expected to further improve biological performance. Importantly, all hydrogel systems demonstrated excellent cytocompatibility, maintaining over 80 % cell viability in MC3T3 preosteoblasts and NIH3T3 fibroblasts *in vitro*.

A major focus of this work was to address challenges associated with preparing composite hydrogels, specifically achieving high inorganic particle loading with homogeneous dispersion while retaining injectability and cytocompatibility, alongside effective chemical crosslinking. The developed systems successfully met these requirements.

Moreover, results from SrRan release tests, mechanical characterization, and *in vitro* studies support the hypothesis that these injectable

Fig. 7. The HA hydrogel and the HA/nHAp composite hydrogel *in vitro* biocompatibility – leachables test on MC3T3 (A) and NIH3T3 (B) cells and direct contact test on MC3T3 (C) and NIH3T3 (D) cells ($n = 6$). Results were analyzed with one-way ANOVA followed by ad-hoc comparison to the negative control using Dunnett's test. Statistical significance is indicated by * ($p < 0.05$), ** ($p < 0.01$), *** ($p < 0.001$), **** ($p < 0.0001$). Biocompatibility threshold of 70 % according to ISO10993–5 is indicated by dashed lines to guide the readers eye.

composite hydrogels may effectively promote bone repair. Designed for preparation immediately prior to clinical use and direct delivery into defect sites, these HA/nHAP-based hydrogels represent a promising platform for advanced, multifunctional therapies in bone tissue regeneration.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

A. Rubina: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **A. Tumilovica:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **A. Scegljovs:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **K. Klavins:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **A. Vaska:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **L. Stipniece:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **A. Sizovs:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis. **I. Novosjolova:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **K. Salma-Ancane:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the access to the infrastructure and expertise of the BBCE – Baltic Biomaterials Centre of Excellence (European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 857287).

This work has been supported by the EU Recovery and Resilience Facility within the Project No 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/1/CFLA/003 “Implementation of consolidation and management changes at Riga Technical University, Liepaja University, Rezekne Academy of Technology, Latvian Maritime Academy and Liepaja Maritime College for the progress towards excellence in higher education, science and innovation” academic career doctoral grant (ID 1086).

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.carpta.2025.101030](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carpta.2025.101030).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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